

Analytical Potentiometry as a Powerful Technique to Investigate Metal-Ligand Equilibria

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The Analytical Potentiometry is shown as a powerful technique to investigate simultaneously existing multiple species in solution and their stability constants. A series of computer programs are introduced for the ease of data handling and accurate determination of stability constants and species distribution. As a first step, the method requires obtaining families of titration curves, using metal and ligand variations. From this, one obtains proton liberation at constant pH both as a function of metal and that of ligand. Calculations are performed to establish the unbound amounts of each reactant taking part in the reaction as a function of pH . The evaluation of stability constants is accomplished by an iterative least squares method. Thus far many complex systems have been investigated by this technique. Besides investigating the complex equilibria, the technique also incorporates several unique features making the method a versatile one in the studies of metal ligand interaction in solution.

THE method of Analytical Potentiometry was first introduced in the year 1973¹. The technique permits the accurate determination of the stability constants and of the distribution of simultaneously existing multiple species in a multicomponent system. Since then, several complex systems have been investigated using this method. Further improvements of the method, as well as the computation procedures, have been made enabling better accuracy and ease of data handling. An attempt is being made here to briefly discuss the method, its application, advantages and future possibilities.

Theoretical Considerations

Let us consider a ternary system consisting of one metal and two different ligands. The complexation reactions occurring between C_M moles of metal ion M , C_H moles of hydrogen ion H , C_A moles of ligand anion A and C_B moles of ligand anion B can be represented by the general equilibrium reaction,

Where p , q , r and s are number of M , H , A and B respectively. The stabilities of the species formed are measured by the stoichiometric equilibrium constants β_{pqr} , expressed in terms of concentrations at constant ionic strength, temperature and pressure.

$$\beta_{pqr} = \frac{[M_p H_q A_r B_s]}{m^p h^q a^r b^s} \quad [2]$$

Where m , h , a and b are the concentrations of free metal ion, ligand A and ligand B . The following sets

of equations define the total system,

$$C_M = m + \sum \beta_{pqr} m^p h^q a^r b^s \quad [3]$$

$$C_H = h - oh + \sum q \beta_{pqr} m^p h^q a^r b^s \quad [4]$$

$$C_A = a + \sum r \beta_{pqr} m^p h^q a^r b^s \quad [5]$$

$$C_B = b + \sum s \beta_{pqr} m^p h^q a^r b^s \quad [6]$$

Where oh represents the amount of free hydroxyl ions.

Based on the thermodynamic expression for the chemical potential, the following integral expression, equation 7, can be derived¹

$$pX = pX_0 + \int_{pH_0}^{pH_1} \frac{\delta H^\ddagger}{\delta C_M} dpH \quad \left| \quad C_A, \dots, P, V, T \quad [7] \right.$$

This permits one to follow the fate of component X which participates in the chemical reaction in the presence of other reagents, provided that the total concentration of these and P , V , and T are kept constant throughout the reaction. The only variation is done on the component X and the resulting proton liberation is observed where X_0 denotes the concentration of the unreacted component X at pH_0 .

This follows the following relationships which can evaluate the values for the unbound portions of metal

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and the different ligands throughout the titration,

$$pM = pM_0 + \int_{pH_0}^{pH_1} \frac{\delta H_i^+}{\delta C_M} dpH \quad [8]$$

$$pA = pA_0 + \int_{pH_0}^{pH_1} \frac{\delta H_i^+}{\delta C_A} dpH \quad [9]$$

$$pB = pB_0 + \int_{pH_0}^{pH_1} \frac{\delta H_i^+}{\delta C_B} dpH \quad [10]$$

Where $pM = -\log$ [free metal M], $pA = -\log$ [free ligand A], $pH = -\log H$, $pB = -\log$ [free ligand B], H_i^+ = moles of OH^- consumed to titrate hydrogen ions liberated through the complexation reactions. Subscript 0 denotes an initial known state of the system.

Each of the expressions (equations 3-6) represent a system of simultaneous equations of the general form,

$$a_{i,1}x_1 + \dots + a_{i,n}x_n - d_i = 0 \quad [11]$$

Where x_1, \dots, x_n may represent a series of unknown stability constants and the elements $a_{i,1}, \dots, a_{i,n}$ may represent the corresponding values of $m^p h^q a^r b^s$. There are a variety of ways in which equations of this type can be solved. Since observed data have inherent experimental errors associated with them, purely analytical solutions are not very useful. Hence, it was decided on a solution which can be obtained by an iterative least squares refinement procedure. The computer program was designed to find solutions for the unknowns of m sets of equations in n unknowns provided $m > n$.

Experimental Design

An important consideration of the experimental design is to keep the volume and molar concentration of reactants constant. For the purpose of using molarities instead of activities, the ionic strength should also be kept constant. One should be particularly concerned in making appropriate corrections in extremes of pH as the measured pH in those regions does not accurately reflect the hydrogen ion activity. In the pH range, 2-11 hydrogen ion concentration can be used to represent the hydrogen ion activity. It should be pointed out that the proton liberation H_i^+ is only a function of titrant and is independent of hydrogen ion activity. One should also bear in mind that the hydrogen ion activities enter into the β -value calculations. So the β -values of complex species having maximum concentration in the extreme region of pH will carry the largest bias.

The initial pH for each titration is brought to the same value before any complexation started by adding necessary amount of acid. In a typical set of experiments, one does notice a difference of the starting pH . This is caused by the various amounts of metal solution added and also the state of protonation of the sample.

It is necessary to obtain the integration constant pA_0 as a first step for the evaluation of equation 7. If the experimenter can select a condition such that no complexation takes place involving proton liberation, pX_0 can be easily calculated from the concentration of the ligand and the appropriate pK_a of the ligand. For example, in the case of a metal-amino acid system, one can select a starting pH below 2 where little or no complexation takes place. The true concentration of the fully protonated form can be easily calculated using the Henderson-Hasselbach equation. The calculated concentration represents the initial condition of the system, hence, the pA_0^+ is fixed. The calculation of the β -values requires values of pA , the completely deprotonated ligand. The conversion of pA^+ to pA is accomplished utilizing the acid dissociation constants for the J-basic ligand, as in equation 12,

$$pA_x = pA_x^+ + \sum_1^J pK_{a_j} - JpH_x \quad [12]$$

Computational Procedures*

Program PLOT-2

The continuous titration curves are converted into digitized tabular form and put on paper tape or cards.

Fig. 1. Equivalents of base are graphed as a function of ligand concentration at constant pH values. Dotted lines represent the ligand concentrations A_1 to A_5 and solid lines represent the data for the respective pH values.

*The earlier versions of Programs PLOT, GUESS and LEASK have been revised and modified to permit more efficient operation. These programs (PLOT-2, GUESS-2 are LEASK-2) are available in both Fortran-IV and APL languages. Computations are being done on a GE400 time-sharing system. All inquiries regarding these programs should be directed to the author in Canada.

These constitute the input to the program PLOT-2 together with dimension statements and experimental constants, i.e., $pK_{a1}, pK_{a2} \dots pK_{an}$ for an n-basic acid. The data constitutes a three dimensional array (x, y, z) where x stands for the amount of titrant (base) used, y represents the pH and z stands for the amount of ligand or metal in the system. This array is stored as (x, y) pairs for a series of constant z values. The program first rearranges this array to produce a new array where the (x, z) pairs are stored for a series of constant y values yielding numerical functions $x=f(z)$ at constant y, as shown in Figure 1. The differential $\delta H_i^+/\delta C_A$ which corresponds to $\delta x/\delta z$ at constant pH (constant y) is obtained as the slope of the function $H_i^+=f(A)$. The program then performs an analytical curve fit to the data $x=f(z)$ using a standard subroutine POLFIT. The series of functions obtained are stored with respect to pH. Then by numerical differentiation, the slope of the functions $x=f(z)$ at the midpoint A_i for each pH is found. The values for the slopes $\delta H_i^+/\delta C_A$ are printed out in a tabular form with their respective pH_i values. In a similar fashion, values for the slopes $\delta H_i^+/\delta C_M$ can also be obtained. Figure 2 is a typical example for a numerical function of this type,

$$\delta H_i^+/\delta C_M=f(pH) \quad [13]$$

Fig. 2. The proton displacement $\delta H_i^+/\delta C_M$ as a function of pH for the Cu^{2+} -glycylglycyl-L-histidine system.

Fig. 3. Unbound ligand concentration pA is graphed as a function of pH.

The program is then used to fit a curve through the points, say $(\delta H_i^+/\delta C_A)_i, pH_i$ yielding an equation in polynomial form. The integration is then accomplished and the integral is then evaluated for each upper limit pH_i and added to pA_0 as required by equation 7. This operation evaluates pA as a function of pH (Figure 3). The numerical value of pA_i printed out in tabular form constitutes the final output of the program PLOT-2. This same method is followed for any of the constituents such as pM whose concentration in the reaction mixture has to be estimated.

Program GUESS-2

This program reads in tabular results of $pA=f(pH)$, $pB=f(pH)$, and $pM=f(pH)$ which were computed by the program PLOT-2. For each quadruplet pA, pB, pM, pH, antilogs are found and then all likely combinations of $M^pH^qA^rB^s$ are performed to give the elements a_{ij} for the matrix A_{ij} by letting p, q, r and s take on values which are likely to represent real complexes.

This Program must be reworked to suit the user's system. The input/output formats must be retained, however the calculating portions defining real probable systems can be altered. The output is written into file I GUESS to be used as input for program LEASK-2.

Program LEASK-2

This is an iterative least squares technique which attempts to minimize the error sum $R=\sum_i(d_{i,exptl}-d_{i,calc})^2$ where $d=f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n; a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n)$ as shown in equation 11. The coefficient matrix A_{ij} obtained from the operation of the program GUESS-2 provides the input for the program LEASK-2. The $d_{i,exptl}$, which consists of all the experimental d_i values, is read and aligned for processing. At this stage, an initial estimate of the elements of the x vector is read in along with several commands which the program will refer to as it goes along with its execution.

In the subsequent step, the program does the minimization of dR/dx . This is achieved by multiplying A_{ij} with x estimates to give the column vector d_{calc} . The difference between this and d_{exptl} is found element by element,

$$(d_{i,exptl} - d_{i,calc})=F_i \quad [14]$$

and these F_i are squared and summed to give $R=\sum_i F_i^2$ which is stored. Next, the x is operated on element by element, i.e., x_k is set to $x_1 + x_{1.k}$. The computation, $A_{ij} \cdot x = d_{calc}$ is again executed and the new $d_{i,calc}$ are used to find new $(F_i)^2$ which sum up to give a new R' . After x has been scaenned completely and a new R' has been found which is smaller than R_i , this new x' will be stored together with R' . The program then loops back and goes through the logic and arithmetic again to give R'' . If $R'' < R'$, then x will be stored and another iteration will be initiated. However, if $R'' > R'$, then x will be accepted as the

solution vector corresponding to the minimum deviation of the calculated from the experimental results and will be printed out in tabular form. There are a number of criteria built into the program for acceptable convergence. Only a predetermined number of oscillations about a constant value of R are allowed. Also the number of iterations are limited. One constraint is that throughout the minimization procedure, the x_i 's are not permitted to assume negative values. After the minimum $x_{m,n}$ is found, the matrix A_{ij} is multiplied element by element with x. The products are printed out in tabular form. These represent the species distribution of all the complexes found in the system analyzed. A typical species distribution in a ternary

Applications

Binary Metal Amino Acid Complexes

The first attempt to use the method of Analytical Potentiometry was in the investigation of the equilibria in the Cu^{2+} -L-histidine system. This was of particular interest since the Cu^{2+} -L-histidine complex was isolated from normal human blood serum². The complete species distribution and stability constants of the complex species in the Cu^{2+} -L-histidine system were carried out in the pH range 2-11⁸. The β -values obtained are found in close agreement with those obtained by other authors⁴⁻⁸ (Table 1). In addition, we found that a new species MH_{-1}A_2 appears at high

TABLE 1—LOG STABILITY CONSTANTS (LOG β_{pqr}) OF COMPLEX SPECIES $\text{M}_p\text{H}_q\text{A}_r$ ($\text{M}=\text{Cu}^{2+}$, $\text{A}=\text{L-HISTIDINE}$) IN THE Cu^{2+} -L-HISTIDINE SYSTEM; STANDARD DEVIATIONS (S (LOG β_{pqr})) ARE SHOWN IN PARENTHESIS

			log β_{pqr}					
			By Analytical Potentiometry (0.15 M NaCl, 25°)		Other References			
p	q	r		Ref. 4 (0.1M $\text{KNO}_3, 25^\circ$)	Ref. 5 (0.15M $\text{KNO}_3, 37^\circ$)	Ref. 6 (0.15M $\text{KCl}, 25^\circ$)	Ref. 7 (γ 2 0.01, 25°)	Ref. 8 (0.2M $\text{KNO}_3, 25^\circ$)
0	1	1	9.111 (0.007)	9.117 (0.005)	8.916	9.08	9.16	9.17
0	2	1	15.170 (0.010)	15.158 (0.006)	14.872	15.06	15.16	15.25
0	3	1	16.999 (0.016)	16.92 (0.140)	17.113		16.98	17.02
1	1	1	14.180 (0.009)	14.062 (0.001)	14.03			
1	0	1	10.200 (0.019)	10.13 (0.001)	9.79	10.21	10.56	10.30
1	-1	1	2.000 (0.320)	2.13 (0.010)	2.17			
1	2	2	26.913 (0.090)	26.85 (0.020)				
1	1	2	24.007 (0.057)	23.645 (0.002)	23.05			
1	0	2	18.453 (0.008)	18.10 (0.001)	17.41	18.53	18.81	
2	-2	2	8.043 (0.398)	8.016 (0.004)	6.97			
1	-1	2	7.710 (0.036)					

system is shown in Figure 4. According to the relation $[\text{M}_p\text{H}_q\text{A}_r] = \beta_{pqr} a_i^i$, each column will represent the concentration of the species at pH_i values and the associated x_i will represent the stability constant for that species.

Fig. 4. Species distribution in the ternary glycylglycyl-L-histidine-N-methyl amide- Cu^{2+} -L-histidine system as a function of pH. Curve 1, unbound Cu^{2+} ; curve 2, MHB; curve 3, MB; curve 4, MHB_2 ; curve 5, MB_2 ; curve 6, MH_{-3}A ; curve 7, MH_2AB ; curve 8, MH_{-1}AB ; curve 9, MH_{-2}AB ($C_M=1.776 \times 10^{-4}\text{M}$, $C_A=7.016 \times 10^{-4}\text{M}$, $C_B=8.016 \times 10^{-4}\text{M}$).

pH in appreciable amounts reading about 20% of the total bound Cu^{2+} at pH 10 and exceeding that amount at higher pH values. The delineation of the complete species distribution in this system has helped greatly in the elucidation of the structures of the species in the Cu^{2+} -L-histidine system by physicochemical techniques⁹.

The method was then employed to investigate the Cu^{2+} -L-serine, Cu^{2+} -L-glutamine and Cu^{2+} -L-threonine systems^{10,11}. The results of these systems are consistent with earlier reports^{4,12-15} as shown in Table 2. In the studies of the Cu^{2+} -L-serine system, it was possible to detect two new species MH_{-1}A_3 and MH_{-2}A_2 in addition to the species MA and MA_2 . Similar results were obtained with Cu^{2+} -L-threonine system. However, Cu^{2+} -L-glutamine system showed the presence of species MA and MA_2 only.

Ternary Metal Amino Acid Complexes

The ternary systems studied by this method included L-histidine- Cu^{2+} -L-serine, L-histidine- Cu^{2+} -L-glutamine and L-histidine- Cu^{2+} -L-threonine^{10,11}. These ternary complexes were shown to be important physiologically⁹. The species and their stability constants are shown in

TABLE 2—LOG STABILITY CONSTANTS (LOG β_{pqr}) OF COMPLEX SPECIES $M_pH_qA_r$ ($M=Cu^{2+}$, $A=L$ -SERINE, L -GLUTAMINE OR L -THREONINE) IN Cu^{2+} - L -SERINE, Cu^{2+} - L -GLUTAMINE AND Cu^{2+} - L -THREONINE SYSTEMS; STANDARD DEVIATIONS (S (LOG β_{pqr})) ARE SHOWN IN PARENTHESES

p	q	r	log β_{pqr}		Other References			
			By Analytical Potentiometry (0.15 M NaCl, 25°)	Ref. 4 (0.1 M KNO ₃ , 25°)	Ref. 12 (0.15M KNO ₃ , 37°)	Ref. 13 (0.15M KNO ₃ , 37°)	Ref. 14 (0.2M KCl, 25°)	Ref. 15 (I=0.05 KCl, 25°)
Cu²⁺-L-Serine								
0	1	1	8.954 (0.009)		8.839	0.02		2.15
0	2	1	11.163 (0.006)		11.019	0.02		11.30
1	0	1	8.010 (0.008)		7.56	0.01		7.93
1	0	2	14.583 (0.010)		14.01	0.01		14.48
1	-1	2	4.772 (0.010)					
1	-2	2	-6.18 (0.02)					
Cu²⁺-L-Glutamine								
0	1	1	8.97 (0.009)				8.83	9.00
0	2	1	11.360 (0.005)				10.98	11.15
1	0	1	7.765 (0.004)				7.24	7.62
1	0	2	14.613 (0.005)				13.40	14.00
Cu²⁺-L-Threonine								
0	1	1	8.954 (0.009)	8.958 (0.004)				2.24
0	2	1	11.163 (0.008)	11.166 (0.010)				11.22
1	0	1	8.006 (0.009)	8.009 (0.002)				8.02
1	0	2	14.688 (0.002)	14.712 (0.002)				14.72
1	-1	2	4.750 (0.040)	4.780 (0.005)				
1	-2	2	-6.17 (0.15)	-6.14 (0.02)				

 TABLE 3—LOG STABILITY CONSTANTS (LOG β_{pqrs}) OF COMPLEX SPECIES $M_pH_qA_rB'_s$, $M_pH_qA_rB'_s$, and $M_pH_qA_rB''_s$ ($M=Cu^{2+}$, $A=L$ -HISTIDINE, $B'=L$ -SERINE, $B''=L$ -GLUTAMINE, $B'''=L$ -THREONINE) IN THE TERNARY SYSTEMS: L -HISTIDINE- Cu^{2+} - L -SERINE, L -HISTIDINE- Cu^{2+} - L -GLUTAMINE AND L -HISTIDINE- Cu^{2+} - L -THREONINE; STANDARD DEVIATIONS (S (LOG β_{pqrs})) ARE SHOWN IN PARENTHESES

p	q	r	s'	s''	s'''	Log β_{pqrs}	
						By Analytical Potentiometry (0.15 M NaCl, 25°)	Other References Ref. 4 (0.1 M KNO ₃ , 25°)
L-Histidine-Cu(II)-L-Serine							
1	-1	1	1			6.90	(0.05)
1	0	1	1			17.540	(0.008)
1	1	1	1			21.703	(0.010)
L-Histidine-Cu(II)-L-Glutamine							
1	0	1		1		17.624	(0.009)
1	1	1		1		21.654	(0.020)
L-Histidine-Cu²⁺-L-Threonine							
1	-1	1			1	6.96	(0.03)
1	0	1			1	17.553	(0.009)
1	1	1			1	21.831	(0.010)

Table 3. The stability of the ternary complexes showed a higher value than what would be predicted on theoretical grounds based on observations on the isolated binary systems. In the L-histidine- Cu^{2+} -L-serine system, three mixed ligand complexes MHAB, MAB and MH_{-1} AB were detected in addition to the binary complexes of each individual amino acids. Some species which do exist in the binary systems: Cu^{2+} -L-histidine and Cu^{2+} -L-serine, have not been detected in appreciable amounts in the ternary system. There was about 35% of Cu^{2+} present in the protonated mixed ligand complex MHAB at pH 5. With increasing pH, the mixed complex MAB was formed and accounted for about

75% of Cu^{2+} in the pH range 5.5-9. At $pH > 9.5$, significant amounts of a mixed complex species MH_{-1} AB was formed. A very similar result and a comparable stability constants of the species were observed in the L-histidine- Cu^{2+} -L-threonine system. Only two ternary complexes, MAB and MHAB, were detected in the L-histidine Cu^{2+} -L-glutamine system.

Binary Metal-Peptide Complexes

The results of the binary metal-peptide complexes studied by Analytical Potentiometry are summarized in Table 4.

TABLE 4—LOG STABILITY CONSTANT ($\log \beta_{pqr}$) OF COMPLEX SPECIES $M_p H_q A_r$ ($M=Cu^{2+}$, $A=peptide$) IN 0.15 M NaCl AT 25°, OBTAINED BY ANALYTICAL POTENTIOMETRY.

p	q	r	$\log \beta_{pqr}$
Cu²⁺-Glycylglycyl-L-histidine			
0	3	1	8.040
0	2	1	14.780
0	1	1	17.500
1	0	1	9.220
1	-1	1	3.648
1	-2	1	-1.991
Cu²⁺-Glycylglycyl-L-histidine-N-methyl amide			
0	2	1	14.47
0	1	1	8.00
1	-2	1	-0.479
Cu²⁺-L-Aspartyl-L-alanyl-L-histidine-N-methyl amide			
0	3	1	17.27
0	2	1	14.29
0	1	1	7.73
1	0	1	8.39
1	-1	2	10.01
1	-2	1	-0.55
Zn²⁺-Glycyl-L-tyrosine			
0	3	1	21.295
0	2	1	18.230
0	1	1	10.054
1	1	1	13.483
1	2	2	26.312
1	1	2	17.803
1	0	2	8.142
1	-1	2	-1.408
1	-2	2	-11.842
Co²⁺-Glycyl-L-tyrosine			
1	1	1	13.075
1	2	2	25.486
1	1	2	16.445
1	0	2	6.944
1	-2	2	-3.042
1	-2	2	-13.332

The first peptide complex investigated was glycylglycyl-L-histidine, a peptide which was designed to mimic the Cu^{2+} -transport site of human albumin¹⁶⁻²². A maximum of three protons can be liberated from this peptide upon titration with strong base in the pH range 1 to 11. If the pK_a values of the different buffering groups are separated by more than two units, then the Henderson-Hasselbach equation can be applied to the titration data directly. However, in this peptide, the buffering regions of two protonated groups are overlapping and consequently it was not possible to use the above technique. The problem was solved by setting up and solving a system of simultaneous equations in two unknowns. Starting from the following definition,

$$\bar{n}_H = \frac{Q}{\sum \beta_q ah^q} \quad [15]$$

and rearranging the equation and setting the upper limit of overlapping buffering regions to two ($Q=2$), we obtain,

$$\bar{n}_H = \frac{\beta_1 h + 2\beta_2 h^2}{1 + \beta_1 h + \beta_2 h^2} \quad [16]$$

From this, we get,

$$\bar{n}_H = \beta_1 (1 - \bar{n}_H) h + \beta_2 (2 - \bar{n}_H) h^2 \quad [17]$$

where \bar{n}_H and h are experimental data obtained from a series of titration curves which differ only in their total ligand concentration. As previously stated¹, it can be shown

$$\bar{n}_H = Q - \frac{\delta H_1^+}{\delta C_A} \quad [18]$$

then, inserting equation 18 into equation 17, we get, for the case of $Q=2$,

$$(2 - \frac{\delta H_1^+}{\delta C_A}) = \beta_1 (\frac{\delta H_1^+}{\delta C_A} - 1) h + \beta_2 (\frac{\delta H_1^+}{\delta C_A}) h^2 \quad [19]$$

The sets of simultaneous linear equations obtained can be solved conveniently by an iterative least squares minimization technique.

The resulting output of the PLOT-2 program of the proton-glycylglycyl-L-histidine system gave the proton liberation data $\delta H_1^+ / \delta C_A = f(pH)$. These data were inserted into equation above at discrete steps of pH yielding a set of simultaneous equations which, in turn, were solved for the unknown values β_{020} and β_{010} . Since the buffering region of the third dissociable proton was removed more than 2 pH units away from that of the next neighbouring group, the data $\delta H_1^+ / \delta C_A = f(pH)$ were treated separately, using a NXM matrix where $N=1$ to evaluate β_{030} . The refined values $\log \beta_{pqr}$ of the successive protonated species HA , H_2A and H_3A are listed in Table 4. Calculation of the values of β_{pqr} showed that the complex species MA , $MH_{-1}A$ and $MH_{-2}A$ were required to give a minimum error solution for the matrix. The deprotonation of species MA and $MH_{-1}A$ was very rapid over a narrow pH range (pH 4.5 to 6.0), these species never reaching significant individual concentrations. Above pH 6.0, the major species was $MH_{-2}A$.

In the subsequent studies, the peptide derivative, glycylglycyl-L-histidine-N-methyl amide was designed to approximate the native protein more closely²³⁻²⁵. This peptide derivative was investigated by the same technique and it was found that only one complex species $MH_{-2}A$ was required to give a minimum error solution in the pH range 4.0-10.8. Even though the structures for the complexes of Cu^{2+} -glycylglycyl-L-histidine-N-methyl amide and Cu^{2+} -glycylglycyl-L-histidine are similar, the former complex shows a higher stability than the latter one, $\log \beta_{1-21} = -0.479$ and $\log \beta_{1-21} = -1.99$ respectively (Table 4).

This technique was then employed to investigate the metal interaction with L-aspartyl-L-alanyl-L-histidine-N-methyl amide^{26,27}. This peptide has the native amino acid sequence of the Cu²⁺-transport site of human albumin. The calculation indicated that the complex species MA, MH₂A and MH₁A₂ were required to give a minimum error solution. The stability constants are presented in Table 4.

The system containing Zn²⁺ and glycol-L-tyrosine showed the best fit if we considered species MHA, MH₂A₂, MHA₂, MA₂, MH₁A₂ and MH₂A₂. After a similar analysis, the Co²⁺-glycol-L-tyrosine system yielded a species distribution remarkably like that noted for the Zn²⁺ system, except that there was less of the species MH₂A₂ formed²⁸. The stability constants are listed in Table 4. At pH values higher than those required to induce the formation of the bis-(amino, carbonyl) dipeptide metal complexes, MH₂A₂, four successive ionizations occurred in both the Zn²⁺- and Co²⁺-systems.

We have recently synthesized a cyclic octapeptide which was designed to mimic the Zn²⁺-binding segment of the active site of carboxypeptidase²⁹⁻³². The sequence of the peptide is cyclo-(gly-L-glu-glygly-L-his-gly-L-his-gly). This is the longest peptide whose Zn²⁺-binding equilibria were investigated by Analytical Potentiometry³³. It has been possible to detect several species in this system. At around pH 8; there appears to be one major species present in the system.

Ternary Peptide-Metal-Amino Acid Complexes

It has been suggested earlier that the ternary complex L-histidine-Cu²⁺-albumin acts as an intermediate in the exchange of Cu²⁺ in blood between a macromolecule such as albumin and a low molecular weight substance like an amino acid^{34,35}. Since glycolglycyl-L-histidine and glycolglycyl-L-histidine-N-methyl amide were designed to mimic the Cu²⁺-transport site of human albumin, the ternary system of both the peptides with L-histidine can be considered a representative of the ternary complex L-histidine-Cu²⁺-albumin. Both

TABLE 5—LOG STABILITY CONSTANTS (log β_{pqrs}) OF COMPLEX SPECIES M_pH_qA_r'B_s AND M_pH_qA''_r'B_s (M = Cu²⁺, A' = glycolglycyl-L-histidine, A'' = glycolglycyl-L-histidine-N-methyl amide, B = L-histidine) IN 0.15 M NaCl AT 25°.

p	q	r'	r''	s	β _{pqrs}
Glycolglycyl-L-histidine-Cu ²⁺ -L-Histidine					
1	2	1		1	28.83
1	1	1		1	23.61
1	0	1		1	17.56
1	-1	1		1	11.05
1	-2	1		1	1.7
Glycolglycyl-L-histidine-N-methyl amide-Cu ²⁺ -L-Histidine					
1	2		1	1	27.75
1	-1		1	1	11.31
1	-2		1	1	3.02

the ternary systems were investigated by this technique^{24,36}. The formation of a series of mixed complexes, in addition to several binary species of varying states of protonation, has been observed in the glycolglycyl-L-histidine-Cu²⁺-L-histidine system. They are of the form MH₂AB, MHAB, MAB, MH₁AB and MH₂AB. The minimum error solution for the system glycolglycyl-L-histidine-N-methyl amide-Cu²⁺-L-histidine permitted only the three ternary complex species MH₂AB, MH₁AB and MH₂AB, while the majority of Cu²⁺ was bound to the peptide amide complex MH₂A between pH 5 and 10. The stability constants are listed in Table 5.

Miscellaneous Complex Systems: Several miscellaneous ligands of biological interest were investigated by Analytical Potentiometry (Table 6). The equilibria in the complexation of Zn²⁺ by N-methylimidazole were investigated in order to understand the role of Zn²⁺ in the active site of carbonic anhydrase³⁷. This study was aimed at following the hydrolysis of zinc-bound water in an imidazole ligand field. It was shown that the stepwise species MA through MA₄ all maximize within a range of 1.2 pH units before the appearance of MA₅ and MA₆ separated by scant 0.24 pH units. Accompanying this unusual pH distribution were "roller coaster" stability constants. The log β values follow a repeating pattern of low, high through all six stepwise species, MA₄ showing the highest stability constant.

TABLE 6—LOG STABILITY CONSTANTS (log β_{pqr}) OF COMPLEX SPECIES M_pH_qA_r (M = Cu²⁺ or Zn²⁺, A = triethylenetetramine or N-methylimidazole) STANDARD DEVIATIONS (s(log β_{pqr})) ARE SHOWN IN PARENTHESIS.

p	q	r	log β _{pqr}
Cu ²⁺ -triethylenetetramine (0.16 M NaCl, 25°)			
1	0	1	20.01(0.02)
1	1	1	23.76(0.02)
1	-1	1	9.39(0.02)
1	0	2	22.87(0.025)
1	3	2	48.52(0.025)
1	4	2	52.78(0.025)
Zn ²⁺ -N-methylimidazole (0.16 M KNO ₃ , 25°)			
0	1	1	7.209
1	0	1	2.380
1	0	2	4.924
1	0	3	6.600
1	0	4	9.214
1	0	5	10.005
1	0	6	11.047
1	-1	4	0.157
1	-2	4	-10.615

In view of the importance of triethylenetetramine (trien) in the treatment of Wilson's disease³⁸ and the uncertainty of the species formed with Cu²⁺, the aqueous Cu²⁺-trien system was investigated by Analytical Potentiometry³⁹⁻⁴¹. The species which gave a minimum error solution and which satisfied the spectral

fit were MHA, $MH_{-1}A$, MA, MH_4A_2 , MH_3A_2 and MA_2 . The high stability of the major MA species ($\log \beta_{1,01} = 20.01$) relative to that of the tridentate diethylenetriamine (dien) complex ($\log \beta_{1,01} \sim 16$)^{4,2} is consistent with trien being tetradentate in nature.

Advantages and Future Possibilities

An important area of research in the author's laboratory is the investigation of metal ions in biological systems. A need was felt to precisely study the equilibria between metal ions and biological ligands in solution. A reasonably non-complicated technique was developed to study simple or complex equilibria similar to the ones encountered in many biological systems. The knowledge of the species distribution in a system is an important criterion to study the structures of complex species in solution. In this respect, the method has helped in elucidating structures of several biologically important metal ligand complexes.

One of the distinctive features of this technique is the use of differential expression (equations 7-10) in the mathematical treatment of the data. This makes the method very sensitive to errors. If there is anything wrong in the primary data acquisition, it is detected immediately in the operation of PLOT-2 program.

The logic in the mathematical treatment of the data and the computations for obtaining unbound metal and ligands are rigorous and do not require any assumptions as to the species in the system. Whereas all the classical methods for evaluating stability constants necessitate prior knowledge or assumptions of species composition before meaningful computations can be performed. Utilizing the following relationship,

$$[M_p H_q A_r] = \beta_{pqr} m^p h^q a^r \quad [20]$$

and assuming $\log \beta_{pqr} = \chi$, and inserting values for m , h and a for different pH values, a pH profile for all theoretical species $M_p H_q A_r$ can be easily constructed. If χ is set equal to $\log m^p h^q a^r$, then all species will show a maximum concentration of 1.0 (provided $p=1$) if expressed in terms of bound metal. This will provide the preliminary knowledge for the species distribution. On this basis, one can judge which species are likely to exist and where on the pH scale they have maximum concentration. If a species is accepted that does not exist, the program will eliminate it. If a species is neglected, then the residual error will be large and the species distribution will indicate on the pH scale where it is missing.

The programs used for the mathematical treatment of the data are specialized and are aimed at economical operation by using high speed remote terminal time sharing systems. While operating these programs in conversational mode, the operator has a constant check on the progress of the computations, which is useful in spotting erroneous input data that would influence the magnitude of the β -values and cause large error sum squares. In that case, the execution of the program

can be terminated prematurely with resulting economy in computer usage. The programs are written in both Fortran IV and APL languages and can easily be adapted to any batch oriented system.

It is not enough to identify a species in the system by simply following the best mathematical fit. Additional criteria must be used to justify the existence of such species wherever possible. A method has been developed to provide such information spectrophotometrically with complexes having characteristic absorption spectra. It has been possible to separate the total absorbance into absorption of the individual species. In this type of analysis, the only assumptions necessary are the Beer-Lambert's law is obeyed and that the total absorbance A_λ is due to the linear summation of the component absorptions. Therefore, for every pH , value,

$$A_\lambda \cdot [pH] = \sum_1^n \epsilon_{\lambda,pqrs} C_{pqrs} \quad [21]$$

where C_{pqrs} is the concentration of the $pqrs$ th species and $\epsilon_{\lambda,pqrs}$ is its molar extinction of the species at a given wavelength for 1 cm light path. The program LEASK-2 is employed to obtain the absorbance and molar extinction of the species at a given wavelength. From the peak region of each absorbing species, the corresponding ϵ_{max} and λ_{max} can be evaluated. The detailed method of data treatment are available in published reports on several systems^{9,20,24,36}.

The method in addition to the stability constants will yield other intermediate data such as proton liberation data as a function of pH ($\delta H^+ / \delta C_m = f(pH)$). These data are helpful in structure analyses. Information about the specific group involvement in a metal-ligand interaction can be obtained if the group in question shows a buffering region in the pH range studied or if the group is fully protonated at that pH . The proton liberation data are unbiased and they are obtained without any assumptions concerning probable complex species in solution. No assumptions had to be made as to the origin of these protons. The total proton liberation, however, must equal the contribution of each species yielding protons when the metal-ligand bonds are formed. In making theoretical calculation of proton displacement at a given pH , it is necessary not only to consider all the species in the system, but also to take into account all possible modes of binding in the metal-ligand complex. Program SELECT has been written to perform necessary computations for this purpose. The technique has been successfully used in elucidating structures of several complex species in solution^{9,20,24,36}.

Extensive automation of the primary data acquisition processes for Analytical Potentiometry is currently underway in the author's laboratory in order to eliminate errors that are caused by manual data collection procedures. Besides an improved instrumentation, automation includes such features as obtaining a series of titrations automatically recorded onto a magnetic

tape and using the tape directly for computational procedures. Systems are also being designed in which the data obtained from the automatic titration assembly and the recording system will be transferred directly to either a time-sharing system or to an in-house computer (IBM 1800) for faster data handling without loss of accuracy. When these features are added to the ones already discussed, the method opens up new dimensions to research in the metal-ligand interactions in Chemistry and Biology.

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